

OPEN ACCESS E-JOURNAL IN LIBRARY SCIENCE (IT)

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Abstracts:

Open Access Journal are scholarly and most of them are peer review journals. Aim of this articles to elaborate the open access journal in Library and-Information science and use of scholarly information for library personnel. This article discuss about meaning of journal, e-journal and types of e-journals with the brief history of print to electronic journal. It also covers the philosophy of open access journal and along with its forms. Advantages of open access journal to LIS professionals are discussed.

Introduction:

Modern libraries and information -centers provides variety of services to support Research and Development, industrial productivity, management, marketing and trade activities and all other programs of development of government and non-governmental institutions. Scholarly communication is a social phenomenon whereby intellectual and creative activity is passed on from one scholar to another. Along with the impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) new advances, new technology born one of that is electronic publishing on Internet. Print journals changed the publishing also in e-journals, online journals, web journals etc. now the era of "Open Access Journal".

A Journal is defined by Webster's Dictionary as "A periodical Publication especially dealing with matters of current interest often of official or semi official publication of special group."

Print to Electronic Journal: A Brief History

The journal is primary medium of scholarly communication. It has a long history. Journal Dev Savants was the first scholarly print journal published in 1965. The recent development in the field of ICT has changed each and every aspect of world Scenario. The format of scholarly publication has changed from printed to electronic media now-a-days. The first online journal developed in 1980's were e-mailed to subscribers or made available through FTP in strictly plaintext format. As serials crisis worsened in the early 1990's

anticipation grew for the potential of the internet to transform the scholarly communication system. In 1998 one of the first Open Access Journal of Medical Internet Research (JMIR) was created, publishing its first issue in 1999. What is remarkable about this development is that it is created by researchers for researchers, without involvement of any commercial publishers and with practically no budget.

Open Access Initiative (OAI) is created to encourage publishers to provide open access to journal by way of the internet. The initiative is a project of open source institute. Their aim is to bridge knowledge gaps between the rich and poor to provide maximum exposure and use of published knowledge and develop common founded for learning and knowledge sharing in research and education. Other institution or societies taking part for the Open Access Journal open to all.

Electronic Journal

The development in the field of information and communication technology (ICT) has changed each and every aspect of world's scenario. Library and information centers is not exception for that, Libraries and information centers are finding it necessary to change direction and diversity in order to adopt the threat and challenges posed by the internet. The ICT has permitted the publication industry also to change the medium of scientific communication.

Types of Electronic Journals

A. Fee Based e-journals:

Those are commercial electronic journals. There is need to subscribe there journals by paying prescribed past. It gives issues electronically or online on internet and brings related information and updates. But the charges are low in comparison with the Print Journal.

B. Open Access journals:

Open Access journals are totally free, no fee requires. Authors of articles, who will see their papers more read, more cited and better integrated into structure of science by giving login — logout facility. This type of journal also called open access journal i.e. open to all. Most of the open access journals follow same procedure of peer review as in traditional or electronic journal. These journals allow copyright to authors or publishers. The journals are published to make available their articles free online immediately after the publication. Open

Access Journal sometimes called the gold road to open access is one of the two journals methods for providing open access. The other one sometime called Green Road is self archiving in a repository.

Forms of open access journals

The information technology infrastructure of electronic most of the peer-reviewed journals can include a wide spectrum of different features.

- ❖ Storage mechanism for the papers and the metadata (static Web pages vs. database)
- ❖ Format of the papers (HTML, PDF, XML etc.)
- ❖ Treatment of graphics and hypermedia content
- ❖ Management of drafts and the review process
- ❖ Indexing and linking to external publications
- ❖ Alerting and personalization services for readers
- ❖ Hyperlinked discussion threads
- ❖ Statistics on readings, citations etc., for authors
- ❖ Security back up, mirror sites.

Open Access Journals in Library Science

The trends of library changed from traditional to the modern era. There are very significant efforts to start Open Access Journals in library and Information Science. Open Access Journals in LIS are collection of home pages of Open Access Journals collected from different source such as DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journal), BUBL, SciELO (scientific electronic library online), PLOS (*Public* Library Of Science), SPARC, Open J-Gate etc. libraries are critical of the terms of commercial publishers "Licensing contracts for c-journals so used scholarly articles for your purpose by the Open Access without restrictions. Briefly the claims made by supporters of Open Access is that it provides global free dissemination, greater impact potential for research, a speedier publication process and presents overall saving by means of cheaper operations.

Advantages of Open Access Journals in LIS

- ❖ Available to all librarians, researchers, LIS students anytime, anywhere via internet,
- ❖ Help LIS professional personnel to update their knowledge frequently
- ❖ Primary advantage of Open Access is that the contents of journals is available to the user/ information seekers everywhere regardless or affiliation with non-subscribing.

- ❖ It is beyond financial barrier, cost saving, time lacking, without fear of loss of document.
- ❖ Help LIS professional personnel at smaller institutions where their library cannot afford the subscribed journals.
- ❖ Academic readers in general at institutions that cannot afford die journal or where the journal is out of scope.
- ❖ Help students/ readers/ general public interested in the subject

Conclusion

These benefits of Open Access gives free, prime, scholarly, full text journals, most of which arc peer reviewed. This includes lower cost great accessibility and better prospects for long term preservation of scholarly works. Libraries should embrace all three of these concepts now and in future. Open Access Journals not only help libraries or LIS personnel but also all the users of their institutions or help libraries around the world.

List of Open Access Journal in Library and information Science

Action for Libraries

ARL: A Biomonthly News Letters for Library Issues and Action

Australian Academic and Research Libraries

Australian Library Lournal

Bibliotime Rivista Elettronica per le Biblioteche

Booklist

Table of the American Library Association Series A

E-JASL : Electronic Journal of Academic & Special Librarianship

Electronic Journal of Academic & Special Librarianship

Evidence based Library and Information Practice

Florida Libraries

Information today

International Journal of Digital Curation

International Journal of Special Libraries

Journal of Information Literacy

Information & Library Services

Library and information Commission Research Bulletin

Library Journal

Library student Journal

LIBREAS- Library Ideas

LIBRES

Libres: Library and information Science Research Electronic Journal

School Library Journals

School Library Media research

Urban Library Journal

References:

1. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_journals_available_for_free
2. <http://ejournals.library.uaiberta.ca/index.php/EBLIP>
3. <http://www.lau.edu.lb/Libraries/free-journals-lisi.php>
4. SINGH S.P. and KRISHAN KUMAR (2005). Special Libraries in electronic environment. New Delhi p-277
5. M Krishnamurthy, Open Access, Open source and digital libraries A current trend in university libraries around the world, Program: electronic library and information system, vol-42, Number 1, 2008: p-48. Program: electronic library and information system 2008;p-48.